
ФІЛОСОФІЯ КУЛЬТУРИ ТА ОСВІТИ

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“I LIGHT MY CANDLE FROM YOURS...”: ANTHROPOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF MODERN LIBRARY SERVICES FOR SCIENTISTS

Introduction. Integration of knowledge and communications, the movement for open access to knowledge lead to the emergence of factors that update the philosophy of functioning and development of university libraries. There is a need to comprehend the ongoing innovations in the activities of university libraries in the world. **Purpose.** The study assumes understanding of the substantial changes in the library services for scientists related to Open Access and the new role of university libraries – a partner in the production, preservation and spread of knowledge. **Methodology.** On the basis of empirical and theoretical methods, the features of modern university libraries are considered. They include shift of the priority vector towards the services for an author-scientist and support of the philosophy of open access to knowledge. The study identifies and analyzes the anthropological aspects of communicative and informational awareness of reality by university researchers and librarians. The realities of modern services for scientists of Ukraine are examined based on the experience of the Scientific and Technical Library of Dnipropetrovsk National University of Railway Transport named after Academician V. Lazaryan. The observations and surveys of scientists, librarians, publishers of scientific periodicals allow analyzing the anthropological aspects concerning new digital library services. The aspects affect: 1) relationship between communicants; 2) explanations of why it is the authors-researchers who have been at the center of the attention of libraries, why they are provided with exactly these services and exactly in this way; 3) levels of impact of new services on both scientists and librarians. **Originality.** It is established that in the process of communicative and informational awareness of reality, there are changes in the dimension of scientists and university librarians, namely, the ways of their behaviour and the communicative features associated with the development of Open Access and the new role of university libraries as partners in the production, preservation and spread of knowledge. **Conclusions.** The leading role of university libraries in the implementation of digital initiatives of scientific communication, based on free access to knowledge, leads to changes: 1) in the dimension of scientists and librarians, namely, the ways of their behavior and communicative features; 2) in the emotional, psychological, physical states of librarians as intermediaries between two conflicting requirements – ensuring stability in the activities of the library and the need for changes in the services it provides.

Keywords: university library; librarians; open access; services for scientists; library philosophy; scientific communication; library support of scientific research; anthropological aspects

When I light my candle from yours, I gain from you without subtracting from you. That's what sharing knowledge is like

(Peter Suber, 2012)

Introduction

The formation of the knowledge society is accompanied by world integration processes in the

direction of the development of science and education, including creation of the unified educational space of the United Europe, which Ukraine aspires to join. These processes occur with the help of two

leading methods of integration: knowledge and communication.

Formation of the new information and communication space is accompanied by transformation both in society and in the mind of a person, the formation of new values and new sense of being. Anthropological aspects of communicative and informative awareness of the meaning of life are that the value of person's qualities lies in the fact that they help not only to live in a rapidly changing modern society, but also to adapt to it (V. Aksenova, 2013) [1].

Integration of knowledge and communications leads to the emergence of factors that form the challenges of the traditional philosophy of university activity in the discourse of the knowledge society formation, renewing the philosophy of functioning and development of the libraries of these institutions, and hence their mission.

In a broad sense, the mission of university libraries is seen as a statement of the philosophy and the purpose of their existence. And since the mission of the universities themselves is the creation, preservation and spread of knowledge, libraries are called upon to contribute to these processes, and their mission always has a common philosophical meaning, revealing their essence.

The need to understand what is happening in the reality of librarianship, and especially in the university libraries of the world, involves referring to documents that highlight the communicative aspects of their activities in today's information space.

Analysis of publications. Reflecting on the development of the concept "Philosophy of Librarianship", William Garvey (William Garvey, 1993) emphasizes that the anthropological discoveries of library artifacts are random. We know that the discovered artifacts speak only about the ways of performing certain library activities, but not about the anthropological, communication aspects: for whom, why they were performed in this way and how they affected the readers and the librarians themselves. "The philosophy of librarianship appears gradually with the maturity of discipline. It becomes a critical analysis of the library mission ("why"), its application ("how it is implemented") and its meaning ("type of relationship between goals and methods of execution") [22, p. 235].

Investigating the evolution of philosophical interpretations of ultimate reality, William Garvey refers to the famous phrase of Heraclitus of Ephesus (544-483 BC) "Everything flows, everything changes. You could not step twice into the same river" [21, p. 206]. The philosopher emphasizes that the relative stability of the Universe is maintained by the tension between the opposing forces of Change and Resistance to it. This kind of tension is felt today by librarians who should act as intermediaries between conflicting demands on the need to ensure stability in the library activities and the need of changes in the management of library resources and services.

Considering the changes in the modern information space and their impact on people, it should be noted that for almost a thousand years a university library was a monopolist in the information service of the intellectual elite of mankind. It ensured the collection, storage, processing and issuance of documentary information. But since such information was discrete in nature and scattered in space, the task of each library and librarian was the accumulation of the fullest possible and qualitative information resource in its local collections. It was the collection accumulation philosophy.

According to this philosophy, the mission of the library as a "repository of knowledge" consisted in the selection and preservation of documents of "speech" intelligence, and the mission of librarians was understood as help in mastering the cultural heritage and classical works of previous generations. "In accordance with such a paradigm, the traditional processes of acquisition, processing, classification, systematization, preservation and spread of information were actively developing in the hierarchically organized communications of the linear communication model of the activity of the university library. All other functions of the library were considered inessential and receded into the background" (T. Kolesnikova, 2014) [3, p. 116].

Today's global changes in the information sphere and in the sphere of higher education and science, Open Access Movement have already brought and are rapidly changing library and information activities, removing / modernizing certain traditional technological processes and introducing completely new ones based on modern computer and communication technologies. At the

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same time, the library ideology requires the development of ways of proportional and harmonious combination of free and proper (necessary), normative (in accordance with library ethical norms) (Ya. Yakubenko, 2016) [18].

One of the first printed texts of which we have record is a copy of the Buddhist Diamond Sutra, produced in China around 868AD. In it can be found the dedication: "for universal free distribution" (R. Pollock, 2006) [27]. Clearly, the idea of public domain, that is, open access to knowledge, has been present since humanity first began to formally transmit and share ideas. Yet the active evolution of this concept has begun only since the third millennium, with the development of ICT.

Influence of informatization, demonstrating the social and genetic unity of communication processes both in society as a whole and in the library and information sphere, changed the character, forms, and functional roles of participants in communication relations.

Thus, the informatization of society, which provided a rapid development of electronic communication, for today's generation of young people, including students, questioned the value of the book (material object) as the main source of information. This is confirmed by the studies conducted among the students of Dnipropetrovsk (2009, 2013, 2015) [2, 8].

Taking the anthropological dimensions of book and electronic communications, V. Markova (2016) [10] comes to the conclusion that gradually the euphoria of the plural meaning, the denial of the integrity embodied in the structure of electronic communication, change to longing for the loss of such seemingly burdensome values of modern era as science, religion, morality, culture, memory, etc.

At the same time, according to A. Onishchenko (2016), it is precisely today that electronic communication, relying on the nature of the library as a centuries-old accumulator and knowledge systemizer, puts it in the category of primary information experts of relevant and objective information [14, p. 5]. Having a new "digital" generation of readers that expects fundamentally new services, the library responds to the challenges of the present, creating new communication models and forms of work, possible within its essence and reflected in its mission.

First of all, this concerns university libraries, which, according to numerous studies [3-7, 13, 16,

25, 31], have a leading role in the implementation of digital initiatives of scientific communication (repositories, e-journals, e-conferences, etc.) based on Open Access philosophy. Applying creative innovative approaches related to the need to expand the boundaries of their activities and deepen ties in general scientific knowledge exchange processes, the university libraries took responsibility for: a) organization of fundamentally new storage forms of the science "intellectual capital"; b) spread of scientific research results of scientists; c) providing sustainable access to them; d) creation of integrated information environments in accordance with the profile of the activities of university science; e) popularizing the achievements of science in society; f) information analysis and infometric diagnostics of the scientific documentary flow of universities, etc.

It is beyond argument, as W.P. Lougee (2002) emphasizes, that the mission (and hence, the philosophical meaning) of university libraries meanwhile was transformed: more generally, it shifted from the management of scientific products to the management of scientific processes [25].

But the researchers M. Salanova, S. Llorens, E. Cifre (2013) are wondering if the new digital services of the library are very much in demand by researchers and make its role more significant among the university community, why librarians often experience (techno) stress, discomfort, anxiety and physical problems when using information and computer technology? [30].

A. Khan, H. Rehman, and Sh. Rehman (2013) note that the library's quality work can only be provided by a librarian satisfied with his/her work [23]. An employee experiencing a technology stress will not be productive, which means that the image of the library as a service-oriented structure of the university will decrease.

According to Ya. Yakubenko (2016), Ukraine is still going through the processes of forming a new library ideology with its reflection of the sense of library labor as a whole and understanding of what the librarian is working for, what results the library is oriented on, the features of the library's professional consciousness [18]. The scientist emphasizes that in these processes the conservative nature of professional consciousness plays an important role: in the first place, librarians still have the task of "preserving" the library collection, and not of its "use" by readers. Only by changing

the priorities of the library work, changing the places by importance of "preservation" and "use" of the collection, the librarians will make significant progress in promoting open access in libraries.

According to the conclusions of A. Shulga, the transformation of the philosophy of library activities is related to specific areas: a) introduction of new information technologies; b) expansion of possibilities for the participation of libraries in research activities; c) approval of new principles of international cooperation; d) modernization of the cultural and educational functions of the library [17].

But, as it seems, this list can hardly be considered complete. For example, it does not take into account the directions of transforming the understanding of the activities of university libraries, which are connected with the formation of a new global infrastructure of scientific communications, changes in the consciousness of scientists, and the rapid expansion of the extremely powerful global factor of science and education development – Open Access Movement.

Therefore, despite a significant series of publications, the problem of understanding the transformation of the librarianship can not be considered settled. There are a number of issues which still have no sufficiently substantiated answer.

In this study, the author focuses on meaningful changes in the realities of university libraries related to servicing scientists in the development processes of Open Science. From our point of view, it is the rethinking of the fact that in the focus of today's attention of scientific libraries – researchers with a new worldview, requiring fundamentally new services, and the librarians who provide these services, that is not sufficiently reflected in the philosophical works.

Purpose

Proceeding from the foregoing, the purpose of the study is to understand the meaningful changes in the library services for scientists, associated with Open Access and the new role of university libraries that are the partner in the production, preservation and spread of knowledge.

Statement of basic material

To answer the question why researchers became the center of attention of university libraries, it should be noted that in recent years we can observe the intensification of worldwide processes of introduction of new models of scientific communication, involving the transfer of interaction in the digital environment area. It is mainly there the today's world scientific knowledge is formed and spreads and the information is exchanged in the processes of formal and informal communication. New models of scientific communication include: electronic journals, electronic archives, educational platforms, databases of primary research results, e-labs, open conference platforms.

Scientists, having different levels both of information culture, understanding of the scientific information circulation in a virtual environment and open access to it, and of awareness of the current assessment of scientific productivity and the development of online profiles of researchers, required knowledgeable and reliable partners in the theoretical and practical mastery of these issues.

Throughout the world, such partners for the scientific university communities have become the scientific libraries that in the last decade are actively forming new strategies for their development. It was they who realized the need to develop, in the next few years, a qualitatively new system of targeted satisfaction of the dynamically growing information needs of fundamental and applied research and supporting the introduction of their results into practice (V. Popyk, 2016) [15, p. 4].

According to the author, the understanding by university librarians of changes in the concept of the research life cycle and the mechanisms of spread of scientific information allowed them to identify the main user of such a system – the author-scientist. It is this category of users (and not just user-scientists) that requires a special attitude and an unconventional targeted satisfaction of information needs. That is, the peculiarity of modern scientific libraries is the shift of the attention vector from services to the reader in general to the priority attention in the provision of services to the author-scientist (Ch. Borgman, 2010; T. Kolesnykova, 2011, 2015) [4, 6, 19].

In order to understand the information needs of scientific authors, one should take into account that the main vector of transformations in the communicative activity of university libraries,

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whose catalyst has become the informatization, is in the aspect of creating, organizing and using electronic resources.

One of the most influential factors in the development of this vector for researchers and scientific libraries of the world became the global movement of Open Access and the idea of science as a collective creativity. Open Science is one of the three priority areas within the European Policy of Research, Science and Innovation. Open science is characterized by: 1) Open Access to Publication 2) Open Research Data 3) Open Scholarly Communication & Citizen Science.

Peter Suber (2012), a world-renowned professor of philosophy and an open access expert, emphasizing the unlimited potential of open access in the development of science, makes the following comparison: "When I light my candle from yours, I gain from you without subtracting from you. That's what sharing knowledge is like" [32].

Scientific libraries were among the first institutions that not only understood the meaning of the thesis, but also became active advocates and practitioners in the implementation of open access initiatives in their universities. The philosophy of free exchange of scientific knowledge, aspiration for basic democratic values, is very organically reflected in the priority activity dominant "University libraries must prove the value they represent for the community of their institution" [5, 35]. Guided by it, the librarians constantly monitor and study the rapidly changing needs of users, analyze possible options for action and try to respond quickly to received requests in order to improve the service processes. At the same time, free access to information and knowledge is a professional ethical value for librarians, which manifests itself in ethical beliefs and in ethical behavior.

The strategy for the development of most university libraries started providing the most complete orientation to the information needs of the scientist as an information donor and a knowledge acceptor (J. Richardson, T. Nolan-Brown, P. Loria & S. Bradbury, 2012; K. Wittenberg, 2008) [28, 33].

However, it should be noted that formation in the university libraries of a qualitatively new system of targeted satisfaction of scientists' information needs aimed at the creation, preservation and spread of knowledge requires a

critical understanding not only of new aspects of the relationship between the communicants "scientist – librarian", "author (scholar) – librarian", "publisher – librarian", "IT-specialist – librarian". Analysis is required for fundamentally new library products and services, explaining why for such a category of users as researchers exactly these services are applied and exactly in this way. The communicative aspect also assumes a comprehension of the levels of impact of new services on both scientists and librarians.

Three surveys were dedicated to the study of these aspects. The surveys were conducted among scientists, teachers, publishers, editors and librarians during the all-Ukrainian scientific and practical seminars of the series "Digital Initiatives of Scientific Communication and Infometric Diagnostics of the Documentary Flow of Ukrainian Universities" (2014-2016, Dnipropetrovsk National University of Railway Transport named after Academician V. Lazaryan). The survey was conducted with the purpose of revealing the level of introduction of digital initiatives of scientific communication in higher educational institutions of Ukraine; improvement of library and information services for library users in modern conditions (A. Myrhorodska & O. Petrenko, 2016) [11].

From the point of view of the author of this article (as the scientific supervisor of these seminars) and the survey results analyzed by A. Myrhorodska and O. Petrenko, the conclusion can be formulated as follows: 1) the introduction of new library services to support scientific publications (their creation, publication in open access e-journals, placement in digital archives, measurement of influence, etc.) are extremely relevant for the university community; 2) the level of awareness of scientists about the full range of issues on the creation, publication of articles and their post-publication support is not sufficient; 3) the levels of competence of university librarians in Ukraine in the main issues of the development of scientific communications and open access are very different and require significant updating. (incl. scientific publishing services, support of digital open access archives, copyright and consultations on open access, evaluation of scientific resources).

Open access resources occupy an ever increasing place in the activity of university libraries in

the world, and in the context of the crisis economy of Ukraine it is the main element of information services. That is why one of the main issues is the philosophical understanding of open access as the processes of free online access to scientific information and its free use.

Today it can already be stated that the initial mistrust and resistance of researchers to the presentation of their own scientific products in open access (for example, in repositories) has been weakened or overcome largely thanks to university librarians [6].

It was the open access philosophy that became a powerful impetus for the development of partnership of scientific libraries with various interested university structures (publishing departments, editorial offices of journals, IT services, etc.) and the creation of research support services in libraries.

Library support for research is defined by scientists as the main service offered to the university scientists to support them as researchers (A. Larsen, B. Dorch, M. Nyman, K. Thomsen, & T. Drachen, 2010) [24, p. 7].

Once in the focus of the library's attention, all researchers – the scientific and pedagogical team, research scientists, PhD students, and masters – become users of an unprecedentedly wide range of services for the creation and support of scientific publications. Some of these services actively influence the further development of the library, changing its place and role in today's landscape of scientific communication. The variety of these services is very wide: from high-quality information support and online access, consultations on the data disclosure strategy, selection of publications for the article, Research Data Management to the development of the information culture and research skills, as well as user strategies.

The opinions of scientists on this matter are interesting. For example, a study conducted in 2015 among the teaching staff of the US Higher Education Area (Ithaka S + R US Faculty Survey) proves that teachers and scientists consider the contribution of libraries in support of scientific research extremely large and useful (especially the provision of electronic publishing services and research data management). At the same time, the faculty staff believe that students of their universities have poor research skills, need to develop skills in critical analysis and information literacy. And related to this, in their opinion, the contribution of libraries

is still insufficient and requires special attention and quick action (C. Wolff, A. B. Rod, R. C. Schonfeld, 2016) [34].

The realities of modern services for scientists of Ukraine can be considered on the example of the Scientific and Technical Library of Dnipropetrovsk National University of Railway Transport named after Academician V. Lazaryan.

Realizing the need to adapt the library structure to changes in the information space, to support digital initiatives of scientific communication and open access movement, as well as to improve the quality and comfort of the researchers in the library, two new services were formed. They cover the most in-demand services by the scientific community of the university. This is the Scientific Publishing Support Service and the Information Analytics Service.

For example, the Scientific Publishing Support Service (or Library Publishing) is a set of library innovative services and creative solutions to support the creation, organization of access, spread, supervision and effective presentation of scientific achievements (publications) of DNURT scientists in the global information space. Among the main services of Library Publishing:

1) Accompanying support of the institutional repository eadNURT (<http://eadnurt.diit.edu.ua/>, on the Dspace platform);

2) Creation of university open access scientific journals on the OJS platform – "Anthropological Measurements of Philosophical Research" (<http://ampr.diit.edu.ua>) and "Science and Transport Progress" (<http://stp.diit.edu.ua>), – with support: support of sites of 2 journals, bibliographic culture of articles, digitization of archives, services of bibliographers, translators, experts in copyright, etc.;

3) Support of sites of scientific conferences on the OCS platform – "Anthropological Measurements of Philosophical Research" (<http://conf-ampr.diit.edu.ua>) and "University Library at the New Stage Social Communications Development" (<http://conflib.diit.edu.ua>), – with support of publication of reports (both in separate documents and in collections), their preservation and provision of access to them, etc. [3-4, 6-7].

The Information Analytics Service is considered by us as a tool for monitoring the world scientific information flow, analysis of the level of citation of university scientists and influence indices

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of its periodicals in the international scientific information space, and as predictive and recommendatory activities to increase the representativeness of university scientists' publications in the international scientometric databases, improvement of own periodicals of the university to world standards, etc.

In this direction, the DNURT librarians prepare analytical reports for the administration and departments, conduct scientific and practical seminars for scientists, individual consultations, video tutorials, bibliometric studies on various aspects of publication of DNURT scientists in the world and on determining the leading topics in the world science development, services to support the development of the online profile of the researcher, etc. (A. Myrhorodska, O. Savelieva, 2016) [12]. It should be emphasized that all services of the DNURT library are free of charge, and the activity of librarians is based on new ideas and creative solutions and open access opportunities.

It can be stated that today the anthropological aspects of communicative and informational awareness of reality by university researchers are as follows. The scientific community of the DNURT: 1) actively welcomes new services of the library; 2) is ready to expand partnership with it; 3) realizes that it is becoming increasingly dependent on the generation and reuse of huge amounts of information (including those created by itself); 4) recognizes that it is hardly possible to cope with the structuring and organization of information flows without a scientific library involved in the development of new products and services in the field of information management.

Having answered the question about some communicative aspects of providing modern library services to scientists (for whom, why exactly such services and their influence on the relations "librarian – scientist"), we will consider the influence of such activity on the librarians themselves.

The profession of a librarian refers today to the most dynamically changing, and the employees of university libraries – to those specialists who creatively overcome the centuries-old stereotypes and long-standing principles of activity.

For example, the key competencies of modern university librarians (as information specialists) are in the field of:

- Information and knowledge services, resources, systems and technologies;

- Preservation and retrieval of information, as well as data analysis;
- Organization of data, information, resources and knowledge;
- Information ethics [20, 31].

We can argue that, although the humanitarian component of the profession of a librarian will be unchallenged, the boundaries between the activities of librarians and IT professionals are gradually beginning to blur. That is, the profession of a librarian is being formed today as humanitarian in nature and technical by means of implementation.

Returning to the study of the evolution of philosophical interpretations of the ultimate reality by William Garvey (1993) [21, p. 206] and the role of librarians as intermediaries between the two conflicting demands – on the one hand, the need to ensure stability in the library, on the other, the need for changes in the services it provides and the organization of library resources, let us touch upon the issue when the librarians have a special type of stress – technostress.

Scientists proposed a definition of the technostress experience at work as a “negative psychological state associated with the use or threat of ICTs use in the future” (M. Salanova, S. Llorens, E. Cifre, & C. Nogareda, 2007) [29].

University librarians are currently working in conditions of information overload, related to: 1) the need for frequent and rapid restructuring of the types, techniques and technologies of work in connection with the continuous improvement of ICT; 2) the current information "flood" of diverse types of scientific objects (publications, primary research data or audiovisual content); 3) the need to find a compromise between meeting current needs and developing opportunities for the future.

Thus, the studies in the Landmark University Library (S. Owolabi, A. Aregbesola, O. Oyesola, 2015) indicate that the library staff specify the following reasons for the technostress: long working time at the computer (82.4%); low Internet access speed and poor technical support (64.7%); fear of new technologies (58.8%); changes in library software (52.9%); insufficient computer skills (52.9%), etc. [26].

At the same time, the studies conducted among university librarians in the city of Mykolayiv (T. Kostyrko, 2016) confirmed the existence of a problematic situation in the sphere of advance training of university library staff in Ukraine [9]. Due to the

low remuneration, significant workloads, uncertainty of the prospects for career growth, university libraries are experiencing an outflow of professionals with high-level knowledge of information technology. Employment of young workers, who often lack sufficient knowledge and practical experience, increases the risk of quality deterioration of the services provided. That is why the library administrations develop more intensive training activities that allow new employees to adapt more quickly to work in the busy information environment. Herewith, the importance of independent learning and the responsibility of each librarian for acquisition of professional knowledge and skills increase.

It should be noted that an increasing number of modern university librarians acquire the features of a supplier, creator, custodian and carrier of information and knowledge. And this is intellectuality, pro-active stand, interest in the new, sociability, intelligence, technocracy (in a good sense), mobility, ability to respond quickly, perseverance, creativity, desire to promote the prestige of the profession.

Originality

In the course of anthropological research it was established that the modern technological development of society and the formation of a new infrastructure of scientific communications extended the possibility of forming the new consciousness of scientists and university librarians.

It has been confirmed that there are changes in the dimension of scientists and librarians, namely, the ways of their behaviour and the communicative features associated with the new role of university libraries as partners in the production, preservation and spread of knowledge.

Anthropological aspects of communicative and informational awareness of reality by university scientists are determined.

Conclusions

Thus, the anthropological dimensions of communicative and informational awareness of the sense of university library existence are reduced to the fact that it is influenced by: world integration processes in the direction of the development of science and education, network culture development, the Open Access Movement, formation of

new types of communication and a new infrastructure of scientific communications caused by information technology.

The university community as a social environment is experiencing a period of adaptation to network, virtual forms of interaction in communication and information exchange, is manifested in the formation of new communication relations. This is especially evident among librarians and authors-scientists and requires constant reflection on meaningful changes in library services.

The leading role of university libraries in implementing digital initiatives of scientific communication (repositories, e-journals, e-conferences, e-monographs, etc.), based on free access to knowledge, leads to changes: 1) in the dimension of of scientists and librarians, namely, in the ways of their behavior and communicative features associated with the new role of university libraries as partners in the production, preservation and spread of knowledge; 2) in the emotional, psychological, physical condition of librarians as intermediaries between two conflicting requirements – ensuring stability in the activities of the library and the need for changes in the services it provides.

The essence of the anthropological foundations of the library community amounts to successful coping with stress and problems, being active and creative personalities, self-development, first of all, in the sphere of professional knowledge and skills. Among the most negative psychological states of librarians, it is necessary to note the technology stress. At the same time, the modern profile of the university librarians' competencies guarantees the success of their career, highly informative practices, personal initiatives in the field of information management and contribution to the development of the library and the profession of a librarian in general.

The humanitarian component of the library profession is still indisputable both now and in the future. However, the recognized fact is that today the boundaries between the activities of librarians and IT professionals are beginning to gradually blur. That is, the profession of a librarian is being formed today as humanitarian in nature and technical by means of implementation.

Philosophical meaning and identification of the essence of the mission of university libraries reflect their full support to their universities in the

processes of creation, preservation and spread of knowledge created by the university scientific community. Leading philosophy here is that of free exchange of scientific knowledge. Turning to the

words of Peter Suber in the epigraph, one can say that librarians not only help scientists light candles of knowledge and exchange their light, but they also light them themselves.

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"Я ЗАПАЛЮ СВОЮ СВІЧУ ВІД ВАШОЇ ...": АНТРОПОЛОГІЧНІ АСПЕКТИ СУЧАСНИХ БІБЛІОТЕЧНИХ ПОСЛУГ ДЛЯ ВЧЕНИХ

Актуальність. Інтеграція знань і комунікацій, рух за відкритий доступ до знань призводять до появи чинників, що оновлюють філософію функціонування та розвитку бібліотек університетів. Виникає потреба осмислення новацій, що відбуваються в діяльності університетських бібліотек світу. **Мета.** Дослідження передбачає осмислення змістовних змін в бібліотечному обслуговуванні вчених, пов'язаних із Відкритим доступом і новою роллю університетських бібліотек – партнера у виробництві, збереженні та поширенні знань. **Методологія.** На основі емпіричних і теоретичних методів розглядаються особливості сучасних університетських бібліотек – зміщення вектора пріоритетної уваги в напрямку послуг автору-вченому та підтримка філософії відкритого доступу до знань. Виявляються та аналізуються антропологічні аспекти комунікативно-інформаційного усвідомлення реальності університетськими дослідниками і бібліотекарями. Реалії сучасних сервісів для вчених України розглядаються на досвіді науково-технічної бібліотеки Дніпропетровського національного університету залізничного транспорту імені академіка В. Лазаряна. На основі спостережень та опитувань вчених, бібліотекарів, видавців наукової періодики аналізуються антропологічні аспекти, що стосуються нових цифрових сервісів бібліотек. Аспекти торкаються: 1) взаємин між комунікантами; 2) пояснень, чому саме автори-дослідники опинилися в центрі уваги бібліотек, чому їм надаються саме такі сервіси і саме таким чином; 3) рівнів впливу нових послуг як на вчених, так і на бібліотекарів. **Наукова новизна.** Встановлено, що в процесі комунікативно-інформаційного усвідомлення реальності відбуваються зміни в розмірності вчених та університетських бібліотекарів, а саме – способах їх поведінки і комунікативних особливостях, пов'язаних із розвитком Відкритого доступу та новою роллю університетських бібліотек як партнерів у виробництві, збереженні та поширенні знань. **Висновки.** Провідна роль університетських бібліотек в реалізації цифрових ініціатив наукової комунікації, заснованих на вільному доступі до знань, призводить до змін: 1) в розмірності вчених і бібліотекарів, а саме – способах їх поведінки та комунікативних особливостях; 2) в емоційному, психологічному, фізичному станах бібліотекарів як посередників між двома конфліктуючими вимогами – забезпечення стабільності в діяльності бібліотеки та необхідності змін в наданих нею послугах.

Ключові слова: університетська бібліотека; бібліотекарі; Відкритий доступ; послуги для вчених; бібліотечна філософія; наукова комунікація; бібліотечна підтримка наукових досліджень; антропологічні аспекти

Т. А. КОЛЕСНИКОВА^{1*}^{1*}Днепропетровский национальный университет железнодорожного транспорта имени академика В. Лазаряна (Днепро), эл. почта chief.library@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0002-4603-4375**“Я ЗАЖГУ СВОЮ СВЕЧУ ОТ ВАШЕЙ...”: АНТРОПОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ БИБЛИОТЕЧНЫХ УСЛУГ ДЛЯ УЧЕНЫХ**

Актуальность. Интеграция знаний и коммуникаций, движение за открытый доступ к знаниям приводят к появлению факторов, обновляющих философию функционирования и развития библиотек университетов. Возникает потребность осмысления происходящих новаций в деятельности университетских библиотек мира. **Цель.** Исследование предполагает осмысление содержательных изменений в библиотечном обслуживании ученых, связанных с Открытым доступом и новой ролью университетских библиотек – партнера в производстве, сохранении и распространении знаний. **Методология.** На основе эмпирических и теоретических методов рассматриваются особенности современных университетских библиотек – смещение вектора приоритетного внимания в направлении услуг автору-ученому и поддержка философии открытого доступа к знаниям. Выявляются и анализируются антропологические аспекты коммуникативно-информационного осознания реальности университетскими исследователями и библиотекарями. Реалии современных сервисов для ученых Украины рассматриваются на опыте научно-технической библиотеки Днепропетровского национального университета железнодорожного транспорта имени академика В. Лазаряна. На основе наблюдений и опросов ученых, библиотекарей, издателей научной периодики анализируются антропологические аспекты, касающиеся новых цифровых сервисов библиотек. Аспекты затрагивают: 1) взаимоотношения между коммуникантами; 2) пояснения, почему именно авторы-исследователи оказались в центре внимания библиотек, почему им предоставляются именно такие сервисы и именно таким образом; 3) уровни воздействия новых услуг как на ученых, так и на библиотекарей. **Научная новизна.** Установлено, что в процессе коммуникативно-информационного осознания реальности происходят изменения в размерности ученых и университетских библиотекарей, а именно – способах их поведения и коммуникативных особенностях, связанных с развитием Открытым доступом и новой ролью университетских библиотек как партнеров в производстве, сохранении и распространении знаний. **Выводы.** Ведущая роль университетских библиотек в реализации цифровых инициатив научной коммуникации, основанных на свободном доступе к знаниям, приводит к изменениям: 1) в размерности ученых и библиотекарей, а именно – способах их поведения и коммуникативных особенностях; 2) в эмоциональном, психологическом, физическом состояниях библиотекарей как посредников между двумя конфликтующими требованиями – обеспечения стабильности в деятельности библиотеки и необходимости изменений в предоставляемых ею услугах.

Ключевые слова: университетская библиотека; библиотекари; Открытый доступ; услуги для ученых; библиотечная философия; научная коммуникация; библиотечная поддержка научных исследований; антропологические аспекты

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